

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.588 Max: 62.717	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1457 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	 Gabiit Project
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #:	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
DEFINITION Rocky layer beneath				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1455	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay 5% silt 45% sand 50% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery m <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
			Compaction		Color	
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft		<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit			<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original	
Southern Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			
Western Limit			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			
Eastern Limit			<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit			
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:					Is bound to (only for masonry):	
Is abutted by: 1390, 1453					Abuts:	
Is covered by: 1455					Covers:	
Is cut by: 1451					Cuts:	
Is filled by:					Fills:	
OBSERVATIONS Excavated somewhat before rain storm; excavated fully after heavy rain storm → ∴ wet conditions						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: South-west corner of Area B, East half of Room N=6 Shape: Rectangular shape with doorway neck on West side						
For layers complete this section:						
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): slopes gradually upwards to the west.						
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Large and small rocks, increasingly frequent towards the west, mostly basalt & tufo						
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): Increases dramatically to west, starting a quarter of the way						
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight						
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping						
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular						
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
Observations:						

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Subfill under tufo floor 1417, a rocky fill.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	ARR + AMB	on	29/7/11
Revised by	CMH	on	29/7/11
PDFd by	ECR	on	1/8/11
Entered by		on	